

γ -Carbon Bonded Acetylacetonato Complexes of Pd(II)

B. K. SAHU* and B. K. MOHAPATRA

Department of Chemistry, B. J. B. College, Bhubaneswar-751 014

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Bis(acetylacetonato) Pd(II) reacts with Lewis bases such as α -, β or γ -picolines to produce complexes of the composition [Pd(ac.ac)(γ -ac.ac)B] quantitatively where B is the nitrogen base. In these complexes, one of the chelating acetylacetonato ligand is transformed into carbon bonded state which has been characterised by infrared and ^1H nmr spectra.

ACETYLACETONE is a versatile ligand, usually the anion coordinates¹ to metal ion through the oxygen atoms completing a six membered chelate ring. The unidentate linkage through the central carbon atom (γ -carbon atom) is also known for Pt(II)² and Pd(II)³. A terminal carbon bonded complex of the composition Pd(ac.ac).Cl(bpy)⁴ has also been reported. In this complex, the acetylacetonato moiety still has an acidic proton, and O,O'-chelation of it with other metal ions forming di- and tri-nuclear complexes has been described^{5,6}. On the other hand the compound [Pd(ac.ac)(γ -ac.ac)(Py)]⁸ containing central carbon bonded acetylacetonato has the β -diketone in keto form, and hence the possible ketonic coordination [as reported for the ionic Pt(II) complex⁷] or anion coordination (by abstracting the proton) with other metal ions was being investigated in this laboratory. The aim also was to synthesise the *bis* γ -carbon bonded complex [as reported for Pt(II)⁸] using a strong nitrogen donor. As a result, though the *bis* γ -carbon bonded complex could not be formed, a uni- γ -carbon bonded complex with γ -picoline as the nitrogen base was prepared. During the course of these investigations the reaction of Pd(ac.ac)₂ with a number of other nitrogen bases were studied. Nitrogen bases such as 2, 6-lutidine, 2-chloro pyridine, 2-fluoro pyridine, 2,6-dichloro pyridine, quinoline and isoquinoline did not produce the desired carbon bonded complex probably for steric reasons or presence of electron attracting substituents. This communication reports the results of reactions of Pd(ac.ac)₂ with α -, β - and γ -picolines.

Experimental

Pd(ac.ac)₂ (0.25 g) was suspended in γ -picoline (3 ml) and the mixture was warmed to 80-100° till a clear solution was obtained. Petroleum ether (10 ml) was added to the solution and kept in refrigerator overnight. Yellow crystals were obtained which were recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether, yield, 0.315 g (90%). An exactly similar procedure was used for preparing compounds with

β -picoline and α -picoline. However, even the use of excess of γ -picoline and reaction under reflux did not produce the *bis* carbon bonded complex.

Analysis and physical measurements were done as reported earlier⁹. Analytical and ir spectral data are listed in Table 1 and nmr spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The compounds have the composition [Pd(ac.ac)(γ -ac.ac)B] where B is α -, β - or γ -picoline. They are soluble in acetone, methanol, dichloromethane, chloroform and benzene. Molecular weight determination of the γ -picoline compound in chloroform indicated it to be monomeric (M.W. Found 372, Calcd, 397).

Characteristic absorption bands in the carbon bonded complexes are listed in Table 1. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ vibrations of O,O'-chelated acetylacetonato appear in the 1500-1600 cm^{-1} region and the bands in the 1600-1700 cm^{-1} region, which were not observed for Pd(ac.ac)₂, can be unambiguously assigned to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ vibrations of carbon bonded acetylacetonato ligand⁹. There are many bands due to coordinated picoline molecule, but characteristic band due to ring vibration was observed at 1613-1618 cm^{-1} . The strong band observed at $\sim 550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be assigned to $\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{C})$ and other strong band at $\sim 450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to $\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{O})$. $\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{N})$ was observed at $\sim 335 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes.

The existence of one oxygen bonded chelating and one carbon bonded acetylacetonato ligand in the complexes is clearly confirmed by proton nmr spectra listed in Table 2. NMR spectra of Pt(II) complexes of carbon bonded acetylacetonato ligand were extensively studied by Lewis and coworkers¹⁰. In the spectrum of γ -picoline compound four methyl proton signals are observed with intensity ratio of 1:1:1:2. The lowest field peak is assigned to the two methyl groups of the C-bonded

*Permanent address: Department of Chemistry, Anandpur College, Anandpur, Keonjhar, Orissa.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm^{-1})

Compound	C	Pd	N	γ -ac.ac $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	O-bonded ac.ac $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})+\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$	Picoline ring vib.	$\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{Pd}-\text{N})$
Pd(ac.ac) (γ -ac.ac)B where B is γ -picoline	48.1 (48.3)*	26.2 (26.77)	3.32 (3.52)	1670 1637	1567 1577	1618	538	453	333
β -picoline	48.26	26.48	3.45	1668 1635	1565 1575	1615	543	450	335
α -picoline	48.14	26.25	3.38	1668 1638	1563 1523	1613	540	450	330

* Calcd. values are in parentheses.

TABLE 2— ^1H nmr DATA, δ (ppm)

	O-bonded ac.ac		C-bonded ac.ac		γ -picoline	
	CH_3	CH	CH_3	CH	CH_3	OH
[Pd(ac.ac)(γ -ac.ac) (γ -pic)]	2.04(24) 1.92(24)	5.44(8)	2.2(49)	4.32(8)	2.44(24)	7.2-7.4(16) 8.6-8.8(15)
Pd(ac.ac) ₂ Acetylacetonate(enol)	2.07 $\text{CH}_3 = 2.0$	5.43 CH = 5.56	OH = 10.56	[Ref. J. L. Burdett and M. T. Rogers, <i>J. Amer. Chem. Soc.</i> , 1964, 86, 2105.]		

Intensity ratio in parentheses.

acetylacetonate ligand, indicating the two methyl groups to be equivalent. The other two peaks of equal intensity at higher field are attributed to the two methyl groups of the chelating ac.ac ligand. Fourth peak is assigned to the methyl proton signal of γ -picoline. It has been well established for the Pt(II) complexes⁶ that the methine proton of the carbon bonded ac.ac absorbs at higher field in comparison to that of the chelating acetylacetonate. This assignment also holds good for Pd(II) complexes. On being coordinated, the methyl and methine proton signals of the γ -picoline molecule are also shifted to lower field region. These experimental observations confirm the preparation of some further examples of γ -carbon bonded ac.ac complexes of palladium(II).

The probable mechanism of the transformation of chelated ac.ac to the carbon bonded one, may involve the coordinating solvent (picoline) assisted partial rupture of M-O bond of one of the chelated ac.ac molecule, rotation of the unidentate ac.ac around M-O bond to re-coordinate through the central carbon atom. It was also observed that palladium(II) does not form complex containing two C-bonded ac.ac ligand, probably because the existence of one chelate ring might be necessary to stabilise the carbon bonding of the other acetylacetonate ligand. Reactions of this complex has shown that Pd-C bond is not stable unlike the Pt-C bond in ionic Pt(II) carbon bonded ac.ac

complex and Pt(II) complexes containing bis γ -carbon bonded acetylacetonate ligand have been isolated to justify it.

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